

PREPRINT

Comparative assessment of carbonation-ingress modelling in reinforced concrete structures with application to a cooling tower

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ARTICLE HISTORY

Compiled March 6, 2026

ABSTRACT

Among the primary durability threats for reinforced concrete structures is carbonation-induced corrosion of reinforcement. Despite significant research efforts in the last decades, models for carbonation ingress are associated with large case-specific model uncertainties. Therefore, this study compares selected predictive models for carbonation of reinforced concrete. Three representative frameworks are examined: the empirical power-law formulation of the fib Bulletin 112, the resistance-based approach of the fib Bulletin 34, and the semi-mechanistic model. Their performance is assessed in a case study on an existing cooling tower, which provides field data for calibration and validation. Deterministic analyses demonstrate that the different models yield consistent predictions, while probabilistic evaluation highlights the dominant influence of concrete cover and the significant roles of diffusion parameters and model uncertainty. The comparative results confirm that reliability-based approaches provide a more robust basis for durability design than purely deterministic evaluations, with case-specific updating of key parameters proving essential for accurate service-life assessment. On average, both the resistance and semi-mechanistic models seem to reproduce field carbonation depths with reasonable accuracy (11–12 mm versus a measured mean of 14.8 mm). Probabilistic reliability analysis then indicates that the durability target of $\beta_t = 1.5$ is reached after about 15 years of exposure.

KEYWORDS

Carbonation ingress modelling; reinforced concrete; probabilistic assessment; First-Order Reliability Method; carbonation depth prediction; service life; sensitivity analysis

1. Introduction

Reinforced concrete (RC) remains the most widely used construction material due to its strength, versatility, and cost efficiency. Its applications include buildings, bridges, cooling towers, dams, and transport infrastructure. Yet, despite design service lives of 50 years or more, premature deterioration is widely reported, especially in aging infrastructure of industrialized countries [1,2]. These deficiencies raise safety concerns and increase maintenance costs, stressing the need for performance-based durability design [3,4].

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Among the primary durability threats is carbonation-induced corrosion of reinforcement. Carbon dioxide (CO_2) penetrates the concrete cover, reacts with alkaline hydrates, and progressively reduces pore solution pH. Once the passive film protecting the steel is destroyed, corrosion begins, often detected only after cracking, delamination, or spalling of the cover [5–7]. This process is widely recognized as a major cause of service-life reduction and a driver of costly repair interventions [8].

The rate of carbonation is governed by coupled diffusion–reaction mechanisms. Relative humidity strongly influences kinetics, with maximum rates observed near 60% [9,10]. At higher humidities, CO_2 transport is hindered by water-filled pores, while at lower levels insufficient moisture reduces reactivity. Recent simulations confirm the complex dependence of carbonation front evolution on internal moisture distribution [11]. Environmental factors such as wind pressure further affect moisture gradients and can accelerate carbonation of alkali-activated binders [12]. Material composition also plays a major role: blended cements with high fly ash contents exhibit greater susceptibility, whereas curing regimes significantly modify the microstructure and resistance to ingress [13,14].

The modelling of carbonation ingress is therefore central to durability design. A wide spectrum of approaches exists, yet broad consensus on best practice is missing. Semi-empirical models, including the square-root-of-time formulation embedded in the fib codes and national standards, are widely applied due to their simplicity and reliance on limited calibration data [15]. However, their validity is restricted to conditions similar to those used in calibration, reducing reliability under diverse exposures [16]. Mechanistic approaches, based on coupled transport and reaction equations, provide a more fundamental description and can even capture simultaneous chloride ingress and carbonation [17]. These models, however, require extensive datasets on material properties and exposure histories, which limits their applicability in practice [18].

Beyond these established approaches, data-driven strategies are increasingly mentioned in the literature. Machine learning methods such as artificial neural networks can extract complex patterns from large datasets and improve predictive capacity for durability assessments [19,20]. Hybrid strategies combining physics-based formulations with machine learning are considered promising for enhancing predictive accuracy [21]. Nonetheless, issues of interpretability, generalisation, and data requirements remain unresolved [22]. These emerging methods are therefore acknowledged here as contextual background but are not directly addressed in the present study.

Uncertainty in predictions represents a major challenge across all modelling frameworks. Carbonation depths vary substantially due to differences in material composition, execution quality, local environment, and maintenance history. For large surfaces, variability in concrete cover and workmanship further increases scatter. Measurement campaigns confirm significant heterogeneity in observed carbonation depths, complicating model calibration [16,23,24]. Such variability supports the use of probabilistic frameworks, including Monte Carlo simulations and the First Order Reliability Method (FORM), which provide rational means of quantifying uncertainty and verifying structural performance [25,26]. Their integration into service-life modelling remains limited, although their potential for rational durability assessment is clear.

In summary, carbonation-induced corrosion is a critical durability issue for reinforced concrete structures. Semi-empirical and mechanistic models remain the dominant approaches for assessing carbonation ingress. Semi-empirical formulations, although simple and codified, are limited in scope and reliability outside calibrated conditions. Mechanistic models provide a more fundamental description of transport and reaction processes but demand extensive data rarely available in practice. Data-

driven methods are increasingly highlighted in research but are beyond the scope of the present work.

The aim of this study is therefore to compare selected semi-empirical and mechanistic modelling strategies under a common level of input information. The comparison is anchored in a case study of a reinforced concrete cooling tower, where field measurements provide the basis for evaluating predictive accuracy. Particular attention is paid to the balance between the fib Model Code formulation, which is widely used in engineering practice, and more advanced mechanistic diffusion–reaction approaches [27–29], which seek to capture detailed processes but require inputs often missing in real applications. By examining their performance under realistic data constraints, the study clarifies the suitability of each approach for service-life design and durability assessment, and provides recommendations for further research and practice.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 discusses the theoretical aspects of the semi-empirical and mechanistic models employed, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations. Section 3 focuses on extending deterministic models with a stochastic component to enable more precise quantification and propagation of uncertainties. Section 4 presents a comprehensive study of a reinforced concrete cooling tower. Particular attention is paid to determining input parameters and their uncertainties, and to analysing the carbonation rate, time exponent and carbonation depths. The sensitivity of the models to the input parameters is also considered. Special attention is then paid to durability analysis and its sensitivity with respect to uncertainties in the input parameters. Section 5 provides a detailed discussion of the results of all analyses. Finally, Section 6 draws conclusions and provides an outlook for future work.

2. Carbonation ingress models

2.1. Selected models

The carbonation of reinforced concrete is a key degradation process affecting durability, and both empirical and mechanistic models have been widely applied to predict its progression. The CIB/fib empirical formulations remain dominant in design practice due to their simplicity, codification in the fib Model Codes, and minimal data requirements. However, their scope is limited to conditions similar to those used in calibration, with poor reliability under variable environments or when applied to novel concretes [15].

In contrast, mechanistic models such as those based on the diffusion–reaction framework [27–29] offer a physically grounded description of carbonation, accounting for coupled CO₂ transport and chemical reactions, variable humidity, and even simultaneous chloride ingress [30]. Strength of such models lies in flexibility and mechanistic clarity, yet their practical use is hindered by the need for numerous material and exposure parameters (e.g., diffusion coefficients, reaction constants, moisture profiles) that are often unavailable in real projects [16,31,32]. A direct comparison of empirical and mechanistic strategies highlights complementary advantages and limitations (Table 1).

The CIB/fib and diffusion–reaction models represent the two extremes of the carbonation modeling spectrum. Comparing them reveals trade-offs between simplicity and physical fidelity. The diffusion–reaction model by Malami [27] captures a wide range of coupled physical and chemical phenomena that are not addressed by the empirical CIB/fib formulation. Unlike the fib model, which relates carbonation depth to

Table 1. Comparison of CIB/fib empirical and diffusion–reaction mechanistic models for carbonation ingress.

Aspect	CIB/fib empirical model	Diffusion–reaction mechanistic model
Origin	CIB (1989) [33]; fib MC 2010 [34]/2020 [35]	Malami and extensions (diffusion–reaction frameworks) [27–29]
Formulation	Square-root-of-time law	Coupled CO ₂ diffusion + reaction equations
Key parameters	Rate constant A , exponent $b \approx 0.5^*$	Diffusion coefficients, reaction constants, moisture data
Strengths	Simple, codified, minimal inputs, widely accepted	Physically-based, can model variable RH and chlorides
Limitations	Limited extrapolation, calibration-specific	Data intensive, requires many inputs often unavailable
Application scope	Standardised design checks, service-life estimation	Research, advanced simulations, special case studies

* See Eq. (1), where $0 \leq b \leq 0.5$ characterizes various exposure conditions.

the square root of time through a single empirical coefficient derived from exposure tests, Malami’s framework explicitly models CO₂ diffusion through the pore structure, its dissolution in pore water, and subsequent reactions with calcium-bearing phases such as portlandite and C–S–H. It accounts for variable relative humidity (RH), temperature, and CO₂ concentration, as well as the influence of evolving porosity and moisture-dependent diffusivity on carbonation progression. The model can simulate transient environmental conditions, cyclic wetting and drying, and even simultaneous chloride ingress or corrosion initiation. In contrast, the fib model offers simplicity and ease of use in design applications but assumes steady exposure conditions and homogeneous material behavior, with no explicit treatment of transport, reaction kinetics, or feedback mechanisms. Consequently, Malami’s model provides greater physical realism and adaptability to diverse concretes and exposure scenarios, whereas the fib approach remains a practical yet limited empirical approximation suitable mainly for standardized service-life design.

In addition to the CIB/fib and diffusion–reaction models, the Papadakis carbonation model [36,37] remains widely cited and used as it represents a valuable, semi-mechanistic bridge between empirical and fully mechanistic carbonation modeling. It provides useful insight into the influence of mix composition, CO₂ concentration, and water to cement ratio. However, it simplifies many key coupled processes (especially humidity, transient transport, and chemical complexity), making it less accurate under real-world variable exposures or when applied to modern blended cements.

Uncertainty is inherent in both approaches. For empirical models, scatter arises from variability in concrete cover depth, execution quality, and environmental exposure. Mechanistic models, while more detailed, also rely on parameters with significant uncertainty or measurement difficulty. Robust probabilistic tools such as Monte Carlo simulation and the First Order Reliability Method (FORM) can therefore enhance reliability by quantifying variability and providing probabilistic service-life predictions [25,26].

Finally, although beyond the scope of this study, it is worth noting that data-driven approaches are emerging in carbonation research. Machine learning models can identify nonlinear patterns from large datasets and improve prediction where traditional input parameters are unavailable [38–40]. However, their adoption is still constrained by issues of data availability, interpretability, and generalisation [41].

In summary, semi-empirical and mechanistic models provide complementary insights: the former offers practical applicability with codified simplicity, while the latter supplies mechanistic depth at the expense of demanding data. Their comparison underscores the need for probabilistic verification and suggests that hybridisation—whether with probabilistic or data-driven methods—represents a promising path for future research.

2.2. CIB/fib empirical model

The empirical model for carbonation ingress was first proposed by the International Council for Building (CIB) in 1989 [33] and subsequently adopted, with refinements, into the fib Model Codes of 2010[34] and 2020[35]. Its central formulation assumes a square-root-of-time dependence of carbonation depth, a relationship consistent with diffusion-controlled processes in porous media. This simple law has become the basis for codified durability design of reinforced concrete structures.

The model expresses carbonation depth as [42]

$$x_c = A t^b, \quad (1)$$

where A is the carbonation rate coefficient, t the exposure time, and b an empirical exponent. For most practical applications, $b \approx 0.5$ is considered reflecting Fickian diffusion. The parameter A encapsulates material, environmental, and execution effects—such as cement type, water–cement ratio, curing, humidity, and CO_2 concentration—and is therefore calibrated against experimental data or field observations. This formulation has been codified in the fib Model Code 2010 [34] and 2020 [35] and is also cited by JCSS documents in reliability-based assessment [43]. Its popularity stems from its simplicity, modest input requirements, and broad acceptance, which make it practical for engineering design and service-life assessment. In practice, it allows engineers to estimate carbonation depth with limited data and to integrate results into probabilistic service-life predictions.

However, the CIB/fib approach is inherently empirical. Calibration is tied to specific exposure conditions and material compositions, which restricts extrapolation to other environments or to concretes containing novel binders. Inaccuracies can arise in long-term predictions, especially where environmental or material parameters differ from those used in model development [44–46]. As such, while the model provides a rational basis for codified durability design, its limitations highlight the need for more mechanistic or probabilistic approaches when higher accuracy is required.

In summary, the CIB/fib empirical model remains a cornerstone of carbonation modelling. Its square-root-of-time law and codified acceptance ensure wide applicability, yet its empirical nature requires careful calibration and cautious interpretation, particularly when applied outside standard conditions.

2.3. CIB/fib empirical and fib Bulletin 34 resistance formulation

The empirical square-root law for carbonation ingress originated in CIB (1989) [33] and was adopted in the fib Model Codes [34,35] and JCSS guidance [43]. In the form used here, fib bulletin 34[47] expression is

$$x_c(t) = \sqrt{\underbrace{2 k_e k_c (k_t R_{\text{ACC},0}^{-1} + \varepsilon_t) C_s}_{A_0}} \sqrt{t} W(t), \quad (2)$$

where:

- $R_{\text{ACC},0}^{-1}$ is the *accelerated* inverse resistance whose estimate (orientation value) read/interpolated from the fib Bulletin 34 carbonation tables by binder family and water-to-cement ratio W/C [47];
- k_t and ε_t transfer ACC to natural exposure:

$$R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1} = k_t R_{\text{ACC},0}^{-1} + \varepsilon_t, \quad k_t = 1.25, \quad \varepsilon_t = 315.5 \text{ (mm}^2/\text{year)} / (\text{kg}/\text{m}^3); \quad (3)$$

- k_c accounts for curing,

$$k_c = \left(\frac{t_c}{7}\right)^{b_c}, \quad b_c \approx -0.567, \quad t_c \text{ in days}; \quad (4)$$

- k_e represents long-term exposure/climate (relative humidity, sheltering) consistent with the fib practice,

$$k_e = \left(\frac{1 - RH^5}{1 - RH_{\text{ref}}^5} \right)^{2.5}, \quad RH_{\text{ref}} = 0.65; \quad (5)$$

- $W(t)$ is the weather/time-of-wetness function,

$$W(t) = \left(\frac{t_0}{t} \right)^{\frac{(p_{\text{SR}} t_w)^{b_w}}{2}}, \quad t_0 = 28 \text{ days}, \quad b_w \approx 0.446; \quad (6)$$

- C_s is the CO₂ driving concentration (mass per volume) at the concrete surface, converted to the same units as R^{-1} so that Eq. (2) is dimensionally consistent. Note here, that in many applications C_s is taken from ambient CO₂ (ppm) with ideal-gas conversion to kg/m³; see C_a in Eq. (18) below.

Eqs. (2)–(6) give the fib Bulletin 34 formulation applied in this study. They can also be recast in the empirical form of fib Bulletin 112 [42] $x_c(t) = A t^{0.5-n}$ by noting that

$$A = A_0 t_0^n \quad \text{and} \quad n = (p_{\text{SR}} t_w)^{b_w} / 2. \quad (7)$$

This presentation keeps the k -modifiers inside the square root, matching the fib Bulletin 34 grouping, while leaving the explicit \sqrt{t} and $W(t)$ factors outside for clarity. Eqs. (2)–(6) together preserve the CIB/fib \sqrt{t} law while (a) linking the empirical rate to measurable material performance via $R_{\text{ACC},0}^{-1}$ and its transfer to natural exposure, and (b) separating curing and weather effects so that project-specific information (e.g., p_{SR} , t_w , t_c) can be introduced transparently. This structure also justifies the common proportionality $x_c \propto \sqrt{R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1}}$, used later for sensitivity and reliability analyses.

2.4. Mechanistic models (diffusion–reaction type)

Mechanistic models describe carbonation as a coupled transport–reaction process in which CO₂ diffuses through partially saturated pores and reacts with alkaline hydrates. In contrast to purely empirical laws, these models resolve the physics of diffusion and chemical binding, enabling prediction under variable environmental and material conditions [17,36].

A representative formulation is that adopted by Malami et al. [27], which retains the \sqrt{t} dependence but derives the rate from reactive–transport quantities:

$$x_c(t) = \sqrt{\frac{2 D_{e,\text{CO}_2} \Delta C_{\text{CO}_2}}{a_{\text{CO}_2}} t} = \sqrt{\frac{2 \Delta C_{\text{CO}_2}}{R_{\text{NAC},0}}} t, \quad (8)$$

where x_c is the carbonation depth, D_{e,CO_2} the effective CO₂ diffusivity in concrete, ΔC_{CO_2} the gas–solid concentration driving term, and a_{CO_2} the CO₂-binding capacity of the matrix. The natural-condition resistance is

$$R_{\text{NAC},0} = \frac{a_{\text{CO}_2}}{D_{e,\text{CO}_2}} \quad \left(R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1} = \frac{D_{e,\text{CO}_2}}{a_{\text{CO}_2}} \right). \quad (9)$$

Malami uses a hydration-scaled binding capacity [27]:

$$a_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.75 \phi_{\text{cl}} C [\text{CaO}] \alpha_{\text{H}} \frac{M_{\text{CO}_2}}{M_{\text{CaO}}}, \quad (10)$$

with degree of hydration

$$\alpha_{\text{H}}(t) = \alpha_{\infty} \frac{t}{2+t}, \quad \alpha_{\infty} = \frac{1.031 (W/C_{\text{eff}})}{0.194 + (W/C_{\text{eff}})}, \quad C_{\text{eff}} = C + k P, \quad (11)$$

where ϕ_{cl} is the clinker fraction, C the cement content, $[\text{CaO}]$ the CaO mass fraction of the binder, $M_{\text{CO}_2} = 44$ g/mol and $M_{\text{CaO}} = 56$ g/mol are the molar masses of CO_2 and CaO, W/C_{eff} is the effective water-to-binder ratio, P the content of supplementary cementitious materials (SCM) and k its efficiency factor.

The reference effective diffusivity is expressed as [27]:

$$D_{e,\text{CO}_2} = 6.1 \times 10^{-6} \left(\frac{(W - 0.267 C_{\text{eff}})/1000}{(C_{\text{eff}}/\rho_{\text{C}}) + (W/\rho_{\text{W}})} \right)^3 (1 - RH)^{2.2}, \quad (12)$$

with RH being the relative humidity (fraction), $\rho_{\text{C}} = 3120$ kg/m³ and $\rho_{\text{W}} = 1000$ kg/m³ are the cement and water densities, respectively. Environmental modifiers then adjust D_{e,CO_2} to the site climate with:

- RH factor:

$$k_{\text{RH}} = \left(\frac{RH}{RH_{\text{ref}}} \right)^{2.6} \quad \text{with } RH_{\text{ref}} = 65\%, \quad (13)$$

- Temperature (Arrhenius):

$$k_{\text{T}} = \exp \left[\frac{E_{\text{a}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad \text{with } T_{\text{ref}} = 298 \text{ K (25}^\circ\text{C)} \text{ and } R = 8.314 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kJ/(mol}\cdot\text{K)}, \quad (14)$$

- Activation energy:

$$E_{\text{a}} = 24 - 8.7 (W/C_{\text{eff}}) \text{ (kJ/mol)}, \quad (15)$$

- Factor k_{c} accounting for early-age curing [47]; see Eq. (4).

In practice, the model by Malami combines these effects within $R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1}$ or directly in Eq. (8). To reflect the acceleration under wetting and driving rain, Malami adopts the time-dependent fib weather function of Eq. (6), which effectively modifies the exponent of t [35], i.e.:

$$x_{\text{c}} \propto t^{0.5 - \frac{(p_{\text{SR}} \cdot t_{\text{w}})^{b_{\text{w}}}}{2}}, \quad (16)$$

where p_{SR} is the probability of driving rain, t_{w} the time-of-wetness, b_{w} an empirical parameter, and t_0 the reference time in days.

Eq. (8) can then be modified into a form of:

$$x_c(t) = \sqrt{\underbrace{2 k_{RH} k_T k_c R_{NAC,0}^{-1} \Delta C_{CO_2}}_{A_0}} \sqrt{t} W(t), \quad (17)$$

using the same presentation of carbonation rate as in the case of the fib formulation; see Eqs. (2) and (7).

The driving term ΔC_{CO_2} follows the ambient CO_2 concentration adjusted for local conditions:

$$\Delta C_{CO_2} = k_{urb} C_a = k_{urb} \frac{M_{CO_2}}{RT} p [CO_2]_{ppm} \times 10^{-9} \quad \text{with } p = 101.325 \text{ kPa.} \quad (18)$$

k_{urb} is an urban-environment multiplier [34,48], T the concrete temperature and $[CO_2]_{ppm}$ the average atmospheric CO_2 concentration given in parts per million by volume (ppm).

Diffusion–reaction models are more physically grounded than purely empirical laws and can simulate variable RH, temperature, curing, binder type, and even concurrent chloride ingress [17]. Their main limitation is data demand: D_{e,CO_2} , E_a , α_H , moisture profiles, and exposure histories are rarely known for real structures. Consequently, these models are powerful for research and sensitivity studies but, in practice, often require simplifications or calibration against field measurements. They therefore complement—rather than replace—codified semi-empirical formulations.

3. Probabilistic reliability analysis

In durability analysis of large concrete structures affected by carbonation, material properties and environmental exposure commonly exhibit significant variability that can hardly be adequately captured by deterministic approaches. This is why the probabilistic approach is adopted here in order to analyse structural durability considering the limit state of carbonation depth reaching reinforcement through a concrete cover – limit state of depassivation. Following the principles of Duracrete, fib and JCSS documents [35,43,47,49], the application is demonstrated by a case study of a natural draft cooling tower.

The probabilistic analysis considers key random variables affecting carbonation, including:

- exposure conditions – weather-related wetness parameters and temperature,
- diffusion properties of concrete affected by mixture properties and curing,
- concrete cover, and
- a model uncertainty factor to account for the inherent simplifications of the mathematical models.

Distributions are assigned and fitted based on in-situ measurements and local climate records, project documentation, widely accepted recommendations provided in the literature, and engineering judgement. Variables are modelled as normal or lognormal depending on their physical domain and previous experience, while parameters with only bounded estimates (such as curing time) use uniform distributions. Spatial

variability is not explicitly modelled but is indirectly represented through the coefficients of variation of these parameters.

Correlations between variables were examined and found to have only a minor influence on the reliability index when compared with marginal variability. To maintain transparency and avoid introducing unsupported assumptions, all variables are treated as statistically independent.

A significant source of uncertainty stems from the carbonation models themselves. Formulations in fib Bulletin 34 [47] and Malami et al. [27] formulations rely on empirical coefficients calibrated from datasets that differ from the exposure environment of the cooling tower analysed in the case study, and the available literature provides limited statistical information for several of these parameters. This results in epistemic model uncertainty due to imperfect calibration, simplifications in how carbonation transport is represented, and the challenge of extrapolating laboratory-based parameters to a structure with a long-term service life. To account for this, a multiplicative model uncertainty factor is included following previous studies such as [48,50,51].

Sensitivity analysis is a useful tool for understanding how input parameters influence the behaviour of a model, and for analysing how uncertainties in the inputs affect the reliability of reaching the durability limit state. A variety of sensitivity analysis methods exist, ranging from local deterministic to complex global stochastic approaches. The paper employs three distinct methods. First, deterministic perturbations of $\pm 10\%$ identify parameters with a strong mechanical influence on carbonation depth. Secondly, FORM α -values quantify how uncertainty in each variable contributes to structural reliability, thereby combining mechanical influence with scatter of the variables. Thirdly, Spearman rank order correlations quantify how uncertainty in each variable contributes to structural reliability. As a local sensitivity measure, FORM α -values are closely tied to FORM reliability index calculations and help identify parameters with the greatest influence on failure. On the other hand, Spearman coefficients represent a global sensitivity measure, considering the entire range of probability distributions and describing overall variance. They are also able to uncover nonlinear relations among parameters.

Depassivation is modelled using the limit state:

$$Z = C_r - \theta_{x_c} x_c(t), \quad (19)$$

where C_r is the concrete cover, θ_{x_c} is the model uncertainty factor of carbonation depth, and $x_c(t)$ is the predicted carbonation depth. Failure occurs when $Z \leq 0$, indicating that carbonation has reached the reinforcement. The reliability index is determined at specified time instants using FORM and crude Monte Carlo method; see e.g. [52] for details. Obtained β -values are compared with the target value $\beta_t = 1.5$ provided in the fib Model Code 2020 [35] and considered in calibration of the durability provisions in EN 1992-1-1:2023 [53]. Other durability target values are overviewed in [54].

4. Case study

4.1. Structure under investigation

The case study investigates a reinforced-concrete cooling tower located in the Czech Republic, which has been in continuous service for over four decades. This hyperbolic shell structure is approximately 120 m tall with a basal diameter of 90 m, typical for

natural-draft cooling towers (the cooling tower under investigation is hereafter referred to as “CT100/60”). The cooling tower was constructed in 1978 using waterproof concrete (class III, standard cement), corresponding to strength class C16/20. The tower – external surface of the shell, columns and gallery – is situated in a rural XC3/XC4 exposure environment, characterised by moderate wetting and drying cycles and significant wind-driven rain exposure. A view of the structure is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. The cooling tower CT100/60 located in the Czech Republic.

A detailed inspection in 2019 included in-situ carbonation depth measurements, performed by drilling small-diameter holes and applying phenolphthalein solution to detect the carbonation front. Core samples were extracted for compressive strength testing, and the results were recalculated to a cubic characteristic strength of $f_{c,cu,k} = 16.8$ MPa. These tests, combined with long-term meteorological records and engineering judgement, provided a dataset of environmental, material, and structural parameters used for the subsequent carbonation modelling.

Table 2 summarises the key parameters adopted for the modelling. In several cases, direct measurements were not available; values were instead assumed based on standard practice at the time of construction, literature sources, or relevant model code recommendations (e.g., fib Bulletin 34 [47], prEN 1991-1-4:2024 [55]). For example, curing time was assumed from 1 to 3 days (2 days in mean) at 95% relative humidity, reflecting the limited curing durations typical in large-scale tower construction during the late 1970s. Similarly, the water-to-cement ratio was taken as 0.55, consistent with historical batching practices without modern plasticisers, while cement content was estimated at 375 kg/m^3 . The RH factor, design temperature, time of wetness and CO_2 concentration are based on the long-term meteorological data, measured at a meteorological station located less than 0.5 km from CT100/60.

The absence of measured values for certain inputs (e.g., exact curing history, on-site water-to-cement ratio variations, early-age carbonation effects) is a recognised limitation. These parameters were fixed to best estimates grounded in historical knowledge and relevant technical literature. For probabilistic analysis, the coefficient of variation (CoV) values reflect either empirical variability reported in the fib Bulletins [42,47] or literature studies on similar concretes.

4.2. Carbonation rate

This subsection quantifies the governing carbonation-rate parameters for CT100/60 within the two selected modelling frameworks: (i) the resistance-based formulation of

Table 2. Summary of adopted parameters for CT100/60 modelling. Deterministic (DET) values are fixed best estimates; probabilistic inputs are given with the probability density function (PDF), mean and CoV.

Parameter	Symbol	PDF	Mean	CoV	Unit	Source/Comment
RESISTANCE VARIABLES:						
Water-to-Cement Ratio	W/C	Gaussian	0.55	0.10	–	Historical batching; assumed
Cement Content	C	DET	375	–	kg/m ³	Estimated; late 1970s practice
SCM Content	P	DET	0	–	kg/m ³	No SCM; fast hardening required
Efficiency Factor for SCM	k	DET	1	–	–	No SCM, $k = 1$ for OPC
Clinker Content	ϕ_{cl}	DET	0.975	–	–	Historical batching; Malami [27], EN 197-1 [56]
CaO Content	$[CaO]$	DET	0.68	–	–	Based on usual clinker composition
Accelerated Inverse Resistance	$R_{ACC,0}^{-1}$	Lognormal	9.80×10^{-11}	0.42	$\frac{(m^2/s)}{(kg/m^3)}$	fib model [47] for $W/C = 0.55$
Regression Parameter	k_t	Lognormal	1.25	0.22	–	fib model [47]
Error Term of ACC Test Method	ε_t	Gaussian	1×10^{-11}	0.152	$\frac{(m^2/s)}{(kg/m^3)}$	fib model [47]
Curing Time	t_c	Uniform	2	0.289	days	Assumed $1, 3$; typical for period
Rate Constant Exponent	b_c	Gaussian	-0.567	0.042	–	Malami [27], fib model [47]
EXPOSURE VARIABLES:						
CO ₂ Concentration	$[CO_2]_{ppm}$	DET	424	–	ppm	Site meteorological data
Urban Factor	k_{urb}	DET	1.0	–	–	Average CO ₂ conditions without local variation
Relative Humidity	RH	DET	74.6	–	%	Site meteorological data; external surface
Time of Wetness	t_w	DET	0.156	–	–	Site meteorological data
Time-of-wetness Exponent	b_w	Gaussian	0.446	0.365	–	fib model [47]
Probability of Driving Rain	p_{SR}	Uniform	0.146	0.40	–	Site meteorological data; fib Model Code [35]
Design Temperature	T	DET	283.85	–	K	Site meteorological data; corresponds to 10.7 °C
Time of Exposure (Age)	t	DET	15 330	–	days	CT100/60 at 42 years (inspection time)
UNCERTAINTY FACTOR:						
Carbonation Depth Model Uncertainty	θ_{x_c}	Gaussian	1.0	0.20	–	Stewart and Mullard [51]

fib Bulletin 34 and (ii) the semi-mechanistic diffusion–reaction framework by Malami et al. The analysis focuses on the probabilistic characterisation of the inverse carbonation resistance under natural exposure, $R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1}$, and the resulting carbonation-rate coefficient A used in the reduced power-law form $x_c(t) = A t^{0.5-n}$.

4.2.1. Inverse resistance under natural exposure

In the fib framework, the accelerated inverse resistance $R_{\text{ACC},0}^{-1}$ is taken from fib Bulletin 34 tables for the adopted binder family and W/C [47] and transferred to natural exposure using the standard linear mapping $R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1} = k_t R_{\text{ACC},0}^{-1} + \varepsilon_t$ (Section 2.3). Propagation of uncertainty in the resistance and transfer terms yields a lognormally distributed $R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1}$ with mean $13.25 \times 10^{-11} \text{ (m}^2/\text{s)/ (kg/m}^3\text{)}$ and $\text{CoV} = 0.45$ for CT100/60. In the Malami framework, $R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1}$ is obtained from the semi-mechanistic diffusion–reaction quantities (Section 2.4). The resulting distribution is again taken as lognormal with mean $9.39 \times 10^{-11} \text{ (m}^2/\text{s)/ (kg/m}^3\text{)}$ and $\text{CoV} = 0.35$. Fig. 2 compares the histograms and probability density functions (PDFs) of $R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1}$ for (a) fib Bulletin 34, and (b) Malami on a common axis scale ($\times 10^{-10}$), enabling direct visual comparison. The fib-based resistance exhibits slightly larger dispersion, whereas the Malami-based resistance is more concentrated around a smaller mean value.

Figure 2. Histograms of the inverse carbonation resistance under natural exposure $R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1}$ obtained for CT100/60 using the (a) fib Bulletin 34, and (b) Malami frameworks, with fitted lognormal probability density functions.

4.2.2. Carbonation-rate coefficient A

For subsequent carbonation-depth calculations, both frameworks are expressed in the reduced form $x_c(t) = A t^{0.5-n}$, where A aggregates the resistance term together with the relevant environmental and execution modifiers based on Eq. (7) (Section 2.3 and Section 2.4). Fig. 3 shows the distributions of the resulting carbonation-rate coefficient for the two models. The fib framework yields A with mean $2.37 \text{ mm/year}^{0.39}$ and $\text{CoV} = 0.29$, while the Malami framework yields A with mean $2.35 \text{ mm/year}^{0.39}$ and $\text{CoV} = 0.27$. Both distributions are unimodal and exhibit comparable spread, with the Malami-based estimate being marginally less variable.

4.2.3. Comparison

The results indicate that, for the adopted input information level, both frameworks provide very similar central estimates of the carbonation-rate coefficient A , while dif-

Figure 3. Histograms of the carbonation-rate coefficient A obtained for CT100/60 using the (a) fib Bulletin 34, and (b) Malami frameworks, with fitted lognormal probability density functions.

ferences are more apparent at the level of the governing resistance parameter $R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2). In particular, the fib-based resistance shows higher dispersion, whereas the Malami-based resistance is less scattered. After combining resistance with the remaining modifiers into A , the two models yield almost identical mean carbonation rates with comparable coefficients of variation (Fig. 3). This provides a consistent probabilistic basis for the subsequent time-dependent carbonation and reliability analyses.

4.3. Exponent

The time exponent b_{eff} in the \sqrt{t} -type carbonation law (Eq. (1)) governs the rate at which carbonation depth increases with time. In this study, b_{eff} is adjusted to account for site-specific environmental effects according to the fib approach:

$$t^{b_{\text{eff}}} = t^{0.5-n} = t^{0.5 - \frac{(p_{\text{SR}} t_{\text{w}})^{b_{\text{w}}}}{2}}, \quad (20)$$

with $b_{\text{w}} = 0.446$ (see also Eq. (6)). The time of wetness was taken as a site average of $t_{\text{w}} = 0.156$.

The probability of driving rain p_{SR} was determined from directional precipitation and wind data for the site. An initial unweighted mean over the windward $\pm 30^\circ$ sector (solid curve in Fig. 4) yielded $p_{\text{SR}} = 0.194$, which gives $n = 0.105$ from Eq. (20). A refined estimate incorporated directional weighting using the external pressure coefficients $c_{\text{pe}}(\alpha)$ for cooling tower walls from prEN 1991-1-4:2024-03 (E), C.6.1.1 [55]; see the dashed curve in Fig. 4. With coefficients 1.00, 0.94, 0.78, and 0.40 applied for 0° , 10° , 20° , and 30° , respectively, the weighted estimate yields $p_{\text{SR}} = 0.146$ and $n = 0.092$. Both values fall within the range reported for vertical surfaces in XC4 exposure (0.05–0.20), and fib Bulletin 112 supports $n \sim 0.10$ as typical for XC4 vertical surfaces (Table 3) [42].

In the subsequent probabilistic analyses, the exponent is obtained by simulations from the basic variables; the resulting distribution is close to lognormal with mean $n = 0.11$ and CoV = 0.71. Fig. 5 shows the corresponding probability density function (PDF) of n , which is strictly non-negative and reflects the substantial scatter associated with exposure-related wetting effects.

Figure 4. Exponent evaluation according to the fib approach with detailed modelling of wind-driven rain.

Figure 5. Histogram and probability density function of the exponent parameter n modelled as lognormal with mean 0.11 and CoV = 0.71.

Table 3. Examples of ranges of n depending on exposure class and climate condition [42].

Exposure class	Climate	n [-]
XC1 dry	> 60% RH; $t_w = 0$	0
XC2 wet	90% RH to $0 < t_w \leq 1$	0.20–0.30
XC3 sheltered	vertical and horizontal	0.00–0.15
XC4 unsheltered	vertical / horizontal	0.05–0.20 / 0.10–0.30

4.4. Carbonation depths

Carbonation depth is evaluated using the stochastic input models adopted for CT100/60 (Table 2) together with the fib Bulletin 34 and Malami formulations (Eqs. (2)–(18)). In the reduced form

$$x_c(t) = A t^{0.5-n}, \quad (21)$$

the dominant sources of uncertainty are the carbonation-rate coefficient A (Section 4.2) and the exponent parameter n (Section 4.3). For CT100/60 at $t = 42$ years, the prior

(not updated) predictions yield $x_c^{\text{fib}}(42) = 10.94$ mm with $\text{CoV} = 0.43$ ($\sigma = 4.7$ mm) and $x_c^{\text{Malami}}(42) = 10.85$ mm with $\text{CoV} = 0.42$ ($\sigma = 4.5$ mm). Experimentally measured carbonation depth is $x_c(42) = 14.78$ mm with $\text{CoV} = 0.36$ ($\sigma = 5.3$ mm). Note that the scatters, expressed in terms of standard deviation, associated with model predictions and field measurements appears to be consistent, suggesting that the probabilistic models in Table 2 may well reflect CT100/60 conditions.

Including the multiplicative uncertainty factor of the model θ_{x_c} according to Table 2, i.e.

$$x_c(t) = \theta_{x_c} A t^{0.5-n}, \quad (22)$$

leads to an increase in the variability of the x_c estimate to values of $\text{CoV} = 0.48$ for the fib Bulletin 34 and $\text{CoV} = 0.46$ for Malami model, respectively, while maintaining the mean values.

4.4.1. Prior modelling and sensitivity insights

The prior models of A and n follow Section 4.2 and Section 4.3, respectively, and are combined in Eqs. (21)–(22) to obtain the prior predictive distribution of $x_c(t)$. The resulting time evolution is shown in Fig. 6. The prior distributions represent the information level available from design documentation, site climate characterisation, and adopted literature-based variability models.

Figure 6. Prior predictive carbonation depth $x_c(t)$ for the (a) fib Bulletin 34, and (b) Malami models.

The comparison of the best estimates of carbonation depths after 42 years of exposure indicates approximate agreement between the survey data (14.8 mm), the resistance-based approach of fib Bulletin 34 (~ 10.9 mm), and the semi-mechanistic model by Malami et al. (~ 11.2 mm). This consistency suggests the reliability of the modelling approaches based on representative values of basic variables, while recognising that some effects may not be fully captured by the models under considerations; see Section 5 for further discussion. Nevertheless, the robustness of these estimates depends on the available or assumed material and exposure characteristics. To explore this dependence, a sensitivity analysis is conducted using both local perturbations ($\pm 10\%$) and global correlation ranking (Spearman). The results are summarised in Fig. 7.

The perturbation method (top of Fig. 7) shows that carbonation predictions are most sensitive to changes in the water-to-cement ratio, W/C , relative humidity, RH ,

Figure 7. Results of sensitivity analysis by perturbation method (top) and Spearman’s correlation (bottom): (a) fib Bulletin 34 model, and (b) Malami model – resistance variables shown in shades of green, exposure variables in shades of red.

and time-of-wetness exponent, b_w . The significant influence of model uncertainty parameter, θ_{x_c} , was also confirmed. As expected, the water-to-cement ratio has a significant impact on the depth of carbonation. The results for the semi-mechanistic model reveal that a 10% increase of W/C will increase carbonation depth by more than 18% while the respective reduction of W/C decreases carbonation depth by almost 20%. In the fib Bulletin 34 model, the water-to-cement ratio is not a basic variable but its change can be taken into account by changing the value of R_{ACC}^{-1} . A 10% change of R_{ACC}^{-1} causes carbonation depth increasing by 5.5%.

Both models reveal significant sensitivity to RH and b_w and θ_{x_c} . A 10% increase in RH decreases carbonation depth of around 22%, while its reduction increases carbonation depth by 16%. This confirms the well-known moisture–diffusion trade-off: higher humidity reduces effective CO_2 diffusivity, thereby slowing carbonation. In the case of a 10% increase in b_w and θ_{x_c} , the carbonation depth increases by 9.5% and 10%, respectively. In contrast, e.g., the content of admixtures (P), their type (k) and curing time (t_c) appear to be less significant parameters with negligible correlations.

The sensitivity of carbonation depth and input parameters was also preliminarily analyzed based on the stochastic model in Table 2 using Spearman correlations; see Fig. 7 bottom. This analysis considers only the random variables in Table 2. It appears that the regression coefficient b_w has the most significant effect with the correlation of 0.72. Also parameters W/C for the case of Malami model and $R_{ACC,0}^{-1}$ in the fib

Bulletin 34 model, respectively, affect the carbonation depth significantly (correlations of almost 0.4). In both models, model uncertainty θ_{x_c} affects the depth of carbonation with a correlation of 0.40.

The preliminary sensitivity analyses provide useful insights:

- RH is a dominating basic variable – its long-term average for external shell is nearly deterministic for a given location but the deterministic sensitivity analysis indicates that when an inner shell or installation with RH around 90–100% are analyzed, significant reduction of carbonation depths is expected;
- the W/C ratio may vary along large surfaces affecting spatial variability of carbonation depths, its lower value for precast members supporting installations in CTs will also reduce carbonation depths;
- similarly as with RH, a long-term average of CO_2 is deterministic for the site but indicates expected increase for environments with higher concentrations (urban, tunnels);
- the regression coefficient b_w is also an important basic variable but in principle a time series of measurements (over decades) would be needed to improve b_w ;
- the change in the temperature factor k_T in the Malami model might reflect the different conditions on the southern and northern faces of the CT while probability of driving rain p_{SR} helps to differentiate between windward and leeward surfaces.

Overall, the deterministic agreement across models provides confidence in the mean predictions, while the sensitivity study highlights the controlling influence of a limited set of parameters. In practical terms, uncertainties in W/C , RH , and θ_{x_c} dominate prediction accuracy, suggesting that careful characterisation of these inputs is more critical than refinement of less influential parameters. This finding supports targeted efforts in durability design to control W/C and ensure realistic environmental exposure assumptions.

4.4.2. Posterior modelling

To incorporate information from inspection data while avoiding parameter non-identifiability, Bayesian updating is performed only on a multiplicative model uncertainty factor. Let $\mathbf{y} = \{x_{c,obs}(t_i)\}$ denote observed carbonation depths at times t_i . A model uncertainty factor θ_{x_c} is introduced such that

$$x_{c,obs}(t_i) = \theta_{x_c} A_0 t_i^{0.5-n_0} + \varepsilon_i, \quad (23)$$

where A_0 and n_0 are fixed, deterministic parameters adopted from the reference carbonation models, and ε_i represents measurement noise ($\sigma_\varepsilon = 14.8 \times 0.36 \approx 5.3$ mm) and remaining epistemic effects not modelled explicitly.

Assuming independent Gaussian errors $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\varepsilon^2)$, the likelihood function is given by

$$p(\mathbf{y} | \theta_{x_c}) = \prod_i \mathcal{N}(y_i; \theta_{x_c} A_0 t_i^{0.5-n_0}, \sigma_\varepsilon^2). \quad (24)$$

A Gaussian prior is assigned to θ_{x_c} , while the parameters A_0 and n_0 are treated as deterministic in the updating to keep focus on θ_{x_c} . The posterior distribution of θ_{x_c} is obtained using a random-walk Metropolis Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)

algorithm.

The posterior predictive evolution of carbonation depth (mean and mean \pm standard deviation) is shown in Fig. 8 for both the fib Bulletin 34 and Malami models, together with the inspection data at $t = 42$ years. For $t = 42$ years, the posterior predictions yield $x_{c,\text{upd}}^{\text{fib}}(42) = 14.89$ mm with CoV = 0.44 ($\sigma = 6.5$ mm) and $x_{c,\text{upd}}^{\text{Malami}}(42) = 14.86$ mm with CoV = 0.42 ($\sigma = 6.3$ mm).

Posterior summaries of the calibrated model uncertainty factor are reported in Table 4. In both models, the posterior mean of $\theta_{x_c,\text{upd}}$ exceeds unity, indicating that the nominal carbonation models underestimate the observed carbonation depth at the inspected structure. The updated discrepancy factor provides a calibrated, site-specific correction while preserving the original physical interpretation of the model parameters, and forms the probabilistic basis for the reliability analysis presented in Section 3.

Table 4 summarises the posterior statistics of the calibrated model uncertainty factor $\theta_{x_c,\text{upd}}$ for the two carbonation models. The posterior mean values of $\theta_{x_c,\text{upd}}$ are approximately 1.36 and 1.37 for the fib Bulletin 34 and Malami models, respectively, with low coefficients of variation (about 0.06), indicating a well-identified correction factor. Acceptance rates (AR) around 81–82% confirm efficient MCMC sampling. These results suggest that both models systematically underpredict carbonation depth at the investigated site and require a similar multiplicative correction.

Table 4. Posterior summaries of updated parameters from Bayesian calibration with MCMC

Model	Factor	Mean	Std	CoV	Median	$Q(0.025)$	$Q(0.975)$	AR
fib Bulletin 34	$\theta_{x_c,\text{upd}}$	1.36	0.09	0.06	1.36	1.20	1.53	0.81
Malami	$\theta_{x_c,\text{upd}}$	1.37	0.09	0.06	1.37	1.20	1.54	0.82

Figure 8. Posterior predictive carbonation depth $x_c(t)$, including model uncertainties, for the (a) fib Bulletin 34, and (b) Malami models.

4.5. Durability analysis

4.5.1. Probabilistic evaluation

To extend the deterministic carbonation assessment and explicitly account for the variability of carbonation ingress, a probabilistic formulation of the depassivation limit state is introduced. The limit state function for carbonation-induced depassivation is adopted in Eq. (19). The stochastic models of the basic variables used in the reliability

analyses follow Table 2. The model uncertainty in carbonation depth is modelled based on the posterior information; i.e. Gaussian $\theta_{x_c, \text{upd}}$ with mean and CoV based on Table 4. Two concrete cover depth scenarios are considered: (i) deterministic cover $C_r = 20.5$ mm (Case I), and (ii) stochastic cover $C_r \sim \text{LN}(20.5 \text{ mm}, \text{CoV} = 0.30)$ (Case II), consistent with typical scatter reported for reinforced concrete members [43, 57].

4.5.2. Reliability assessment and comparison of FORM and Monte Carlo

Reliability is evaluated using the First-Order Reliability Method (FORM) and verified by Monte Carlo simulation (MCS). The resulting time-dependent reliability indices $\beta(t)$ are shown in Fig. 9 for both carbonation frameworks (fib Bulletin 34 and Malami) and both cover scenarios (Case I and Case II). The horizontal line denotes the target reliability level $\beta_t = 1.5$ considered for durability verification; see e.g. fib Model Code 2020 [35]. Considering this limit, a service life for the outer surface of the CT100/60 shell would be around 25 years for Case I, and 15 years for Case II, respectively.

Figure 9. Time-dependent reliability index $\beta(t)$ for carbonation-induced depassivation (Eq. (19)) for the (a) fib Bulletin 34, and (b) Malami models: comparison of Case I and Case II.

Table 5 summarises the probabilities of failure, P_f , and reliability indices, β , at $t = 42$ years. In all cases, the reliability indices fall below the threshold. For deterministic cover (Case I), both models yield β around 0.9 for MCS with slightly lower reliability indices obtained by FORM, likely due to low reliability levels. When cover variability is introduced (Case II), the reliability index further reduces to about 0.6, indicating that variability in cover depth is affecting reliability with respect to durability.

Table 5. Reliability results at $t = 42$ years (MCS vs. FORM) for the depassivation limit state.

Model / case	P_f (MCS)	β (MCS)	P_f (FORM)	β (FORM)
fib Bulletin 34 – Case I	1.84×10^{-1}	0.90	2.0×10^{-1}	0.83
fib Bulletin 34 – Case II	2.59×10^{-1}	0.65	2.8×10^{-1}	0.58
Malami – Case I	1.86×10^{-1}	0.89	2.2×10^{-1}	0.79
Malami – Case II	2.62×10^{-1}	0.64	3.0×10^{-1}	0.53

4.5.3. FORM sensitivity factors

To identify the dominant contributors to reliability, FORM importance factors (α_i^2) are evaluated at the time of assessment, $t = 42$ years; see Fig. 10. For Case I (deterministic cover), the sensitivity is governed by the b_w parameter and inverse carbonation

resistance $R_{ACC,0}^{-1}$ and water-to-cement ratio W/C , respectively. For Case II (stochastic cover), C_r becomes the most influential variable, confirming that geometric variability in cover depth drives the probability of depassivation. The qualitative trends are consistent across both carbonation models: introducing variability in C_r shifts the sensitivity ranking and reduces the achieved reliability.

Figure 10. FORM importance factors at $t = 42$ years for carbonation-induced depassivation, showing the relative contribution of each input variable to the reliability index, for the (a) fib Bulletin 34, and (b) Malami models: Case I (top), Case II (bottom).

Note that when the basic variables in Table 2 are aggregated into the carbonation coefficient A and exponent n , as in Eq. (22), the α_i^2 -values become approximately 0.4 for concrete cover C_r and for A , 0.16 for n and close to zero for $\theta_{x_c,upd}$ at $t = 42$ years; see Fig. 11. The sensitivity factors are time-dependent: at $t = 1$ year the dominating variables are A and C_r with α_i^2 -values around 0.5; the sensitivity factor of n increases with increasing exposure time while α^2 -value of updated model uncertainty remains close to zero.

Figure 11. FORM importance factors at $t = 42$ years for carbonation-induced depassivation, showing the relative contribution of input variables aggregated into the carbonation rate A and n exponent to the reliability index, for the (a) fib Bulletin 34, and (b) Malami models: Case I (top), Case II (bottom).

Overall, the comparison demonstrates that deterministic cover checks may suggest acceptable performance, while the probabilistic verification may fall below the target

reliability when the variability of cover depth is accounted for. This emphasises the importance of (i) realistic modelling of cover scatter in existing structures and (ii) case-specific updating of dominant parameters when field data are available.

5. Discussion

5.1. Agreement of model predictions and field evidence

The two selected carbonation frameworks (fib Bulletin 34 resistance formulation and the semi-mechanistic diffusion–reaction model by Malami et al.) yield very similar prior mean carbonation depths of around 11 mm at $t = 42$ years, with comparable coefficients of variation ($\text{CoV} \approx 0.42\text{--}0.43$). This agreement is consistent with the near-identical distributions obtained for the aggregate rate coefficient A (Fig. 3), despite noticeable differences in the governing resistance term $R_{\text{NAC},0}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2). In other words, when the modifiers and driving terms are consistently introduced, the two models collapse to a similar \sqrt{t} -type progression for the available information level in this case study, which is in broad agreement with previous studies [27–29,35,47].

At the same time, both prior predictions are approximately one standard deviation below the survey mean carbonation depth ($\mu \approx 14.8$ mm, $\text{CoV} \approx 0.36$). This systematic bias is not unexpected for long-term field applications, where (i) local microclimate at the shell may differ from the reference meteorological station, (ii) surface wetting/drying can be more intense due to wind-driven rain and run-off patterns, (iii) workmanship and curing history on large thin shells may deviate from assumed values, and (iv) material inhomogeneity and microcracking can locally accelerate ingress [16,23,24,35]. In addition, phenolphthalein-based depth readings can be influenced by moisture state and the selected pH threshold, contributing to scatter and possibly bias [16,24]. These factors collectively motivate the use of a model discrepancy factor and data-informed updating [48,50].

It is also worth noting that the posterior updates are similar for the two models, which reinforces a key observation of this study: under realistic data constraints, the performance difference between the empirical fib and the semi-mechanistic Malami model is small once both are reduced to a comparable functional form and anchored by the same exposure descriptors [27,28,35,47]. The added mechanistic detail is valuable for sensitivity studies and scenario exploration (e.g. humidity and temperature dependence, binding capacity effects), but without rich site data (e.g. moisture profiles, time-varying boundary conditions), its advantage in predictive accuracy may be limited [16,17,36].

The Bayesian calibration in Section 4.4.2 offers a transparent method of reconciling prior predictions with field evidence through the observation model in Eq. (23). The posterior mean values of the uncertainty factor $\theta_{x_c,\text{upd}}$, which are equal to 1.36 and 1.37 for the fib Bulletin 34 and Malami models, respectively, suggest that both models systematically underpredict the depth of carbonation at the investigated site and require a similar multiplicative correction. In practice, updating the uncertainty factor can be considered a site-specific model calibration that preserves the physics-inspired structure, while correcting for long-term field effects that are not explicitly resolved by the adopted inputs [48,50].

5.2. Sensitivity and reliability analysis

Both the deterministic perturbation study and the global (Spearman) ranking indicate that a small subset of parameters governs the response. The most influential drivers are the mixture-related resistance (represented by W/C in the Malami framework or $R_{ACC,0}^{-1}$ in the fib Bulletin 34 framework), the exposure moisture descriptor (RH), and the wetness regression parameter b_w (Fig. 7) [27,28,42,47]. These findings are consistent with the underlying transport mechanism, where mixture design controls pore structure and thus diffusivity/buffering capacity, while moisture state regulates both CO_2 transport and reaction kinetics [9,10,17,36]. The strong Spearman correlation of b_w reflects not only its mechanical influence but also its large assumed scatter, which effectively propagates into uncertainty in the time exponent (Section 4.3) [42,47].

The results of reliability analysis demonstrate a difference between deterministic and probabilistic durability checks. With deterministic cover (Case I), a service life related to the durability limit state (considering the target level $\beta_t = 1.5$) is estimated to 25 years. When realistic cover variability is introduced (Case II), service life reduces to 15 years. This confirms that the scatter of concrete cover is an important driver of depassivation probability, consistent with widely reported geometric variability in reinforced concrete construction [43,57].

CT100/60 was designed according to the deemed-to-satisfy rules in the past Czech standards, which assumed a service life of 40 years. Obviously, these rules failed to ensure sufficient reliability; a lower reliability level might be partially attributed to poor execution practices. In general, reaching the durability limit state may lead to the following decisions:

- maintenance plan is adjusted for structures with a long required service life, including small repairs such as patching of spalling and major repairs with replacements of concrete cover and treatment of reinforcement in the most degraded areas,
- monitoring of structures with a short service life.

Note that when CT100/60 had been designed according to EN 1992-1-1, the minimum cover due to environmental conditions $c_{min,dur} = 25$ mm should be taken into account for exposure class XC4 for the outer shell and $\Delta_{c,dev}$ of 10 mm should generally be considered as the additive safety element. Fig. 12 shows that $C_{r,mean} = 35$ mm would provide for service life of 50 years.

Figure 12. Time-dependent reliability index $\beta(t)$ for carbonation-induced depassivation (Eq. (19)) for the (a) fib Bulletin 34, and (b) Malami models: comparison of Case II for $C_r \sim LN(C_{r,mean}, CoV = 0.30)$.

5.3. Limitations and implications for practice

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, spatial variability is not modelled explicitly; it is represented indirectly through CoVs (especially for cover), which may not fully capture correlation-length effects over large shell surfaces [51]. Second, several inputs are assumed due to missing construction records (curing history, exact W/C variability, early-age effects), which introduces epistemic uncertainty [16,47]. Third, the updating is based on inspection data at a single structure age; richer data across multiple locations and times would allow more robust separation of A , n , and θ_{x_c} [48, 50]. Finally, the independence assumption for basic variables is made for transparency; although preliminary checks suggest minor influence, correlations may become relevant in other exposure scenarios [43].

Despite these limitations, the results provide practical guidance. For existing structures, reliable durability decisions require explicit modelling (and preferably measurement) of cover variability; deterministic checks using only mean cover may be non-conservative [43,57]. For modelling, the choice between an empirical fib-type formulation and a semi-mechanistic diffusion–reaction formulation is less critical than (i) the quality of input characterisation and (ii) calibration/updating with field data [16,28,47]. A pragmatic workflow therefore follows: use codified models for baseline assessment, quantify key uncertainties in a reliability format, and update dominant parameters when inspection evidence is available [35,43]. In general, probabilistic design for durability enables more realistic predictions by quantifying uncertainties that deterministic models tend to overlook [58].

Among model-related variables, diffusion processes are critical, with b_w and the model uncertainty factor θ_{x_c} exerting the strongest influence. The sensitivity of b_w underlines the value of time-series monitoring of carbonation depth for model calibration, while the role of the bias – mean of θ_{x_c} points to the need for updating predictions with in-situ measurements of effective diffusivity [59,60]. By contrast, the resistance parameter $R_{NAC,0}^{-1}$ exerts only a secondary influence, suggesting that further refinement of this variable may not be cost-effective [61] and its updating through measurements of carbonation depths might be sufficient in many applications. Surface roughness, captured by p_{SR} , also contributes, reflecting its known role in accelerating crack initiation and propagation [62,63].

The complexities involved in carbonation modeling frameworks, such as the fib Bulletin 34 and semi-mechanistic formulations applied in this study, highlight significant limitations. These models provide useful insights; however, their predictive capability is constrained by simplifying assumptions about:

- material behavior affected largely unknown mix design and execution including curing;
- environmental exposure including the effects of wind-driven rain on a hyperboloid shell, freeze-thaw cycles, temperature effects affected by solar radiation (differences between southern and northern faces of the shell), etc.

It is interesting to observe that for instance, missing information on concrete curing (intensity and duration) introduces significant uncertainty and possibly a bias in modelling. When the average curing time in Table 2 is reduced to one day, the mean carbonation depth for both models increases by about 2.4 mm, approaching the mean from field measurements (14.8 mm).

Measurement uncertainty can be an important issue. Assessments and carbonation-induced corrosion damage of concrete surfaces confirm large spatial variability in car-

bonation depths, but field measurements can also suffer from systematic errors. Step-by-step drilling, for instance, may overestimate penetration due to human factor and site conditions. Reported errors of 1–2.5 mm suggest that part of the observed scatter in data may be attributed to measurement errors rather than intrinsic material performance and exposure [64,65]. This highlights the importance of refined measurement methods and systematic treatment of spatial variability in durability assessments [66].

Beyond the scope of this study is detailed discussion on model predictions under wet exposure conditions to which the inner surfaces of CT’s shells and structural systems supporting installations are exposed. Previous studies reveal paradoxes: in certain parameter sets, carbonation depths remain below 3 mm even after 100 years, reflecting the protective role of moisture saturation in hindering CO₂ ingress [67]. Yet, this outcome may not represent real-world scenarios where drying–wetting cycles and microcracking accelerate carbonation [68]. Particularly in wet conditions, caution should therefore be exercised when extrapolating laboratory conditions to field applications, and further refinements might be needed.

Spatial variability in carbonation depths across structural elements adds another source of uncertainty. Mean survey values, such as 14.8 mm for CT100/60 under investigation, conceal significant heterogeneity across measurement points. Such variability complicates service-life design and reliability analysis, requiring probabilistic frameworks including adequate acceptance criteria that can accommodate structural heterogeneity and variability of exposure [58,69]. Improved data collection strategies that account for variability across elements and within members are therefore needed.

Another limitation arises from the weakness of existing databases on carbonation resistance. Many are based on narrow laboratory datasets, limiting their transferability to field-scale applications [70]. Continuous updating with in-situ measurements can bridge this gap, aligning predictions with observed material performance [71]. This process would allow more accurate reliability assessments and enhance the rationality of durability design.

6. Conclusions

This study discusses carbonation ingress in large reinforced concrete structures. Considering a largely accepted resistance-based model provided in fib Bulletin 34 [47] and a more complex semi-mechanistic formulation by Malami et al. [27] (diffusion–reaction frameworks), deterministic and probabilistic approaches are compared. The developed case study focused on an external shell of the natural-draft cooling tower demonstrates that in this case, deterministic analyses seem to reproduce field carbonation depths with reasonable accuracy (11–12 mm versus a measured mean of 14.8 mm). A deterministic sensitivity analyses may provide useful insights regarding physically important variables such as relative humidity and CO₂ concentration that are key factors defining different exposure conditions (external vs. internal surfaces of the shell, locally increased CO₂ concentrations in urban areas or in tunnels).

The probabilistic analysis provides a more nuanced picture of structural reliability. The FORM evaluation highlights that diffusion parameters and model uncertainties dominate the variability in service life predictions, while concrete cover emerged as the single most influential practical parameter. Unlike deterministic estimates, the reliability analysis quantifies probability of exceeding the initiation limit state related to reinforcement depassivation, enabling direct comparison with target reliability levels.

The presented comparison underscores a key distinction: deterministic methods of-

fer quick and transparent estimates of carbonation depth, suitable for benchmarking and preliminary assessment, whereas probabilistic methods capture uncertainties in material and environmental parameters, thereby enabling reliability-based design.

Overall, the comparison demonstrates that deterministic and probabilistic methods should be viewed as complementary: deterministic tools provide practical benchmarks, but probabilistic methods are essential to ensure that service life predictions meet defined reliability targets. The findings strongly support a shift towards incorporating reliability-based durability assessment in Eurocode provisions to improve the consistency, transparency, and robustness of carbonation design.

The case study demonstrates that predictive capability of the fib Bulletin 34 and semi-mechanistic formulations is constrained by simplifying assumptions about material behavior (with largely unknown mix design and execution practices) and environmental exposure (effects of wind-driven rain on a hyperboloid shell, freeze-thaw cycles, etc.). These notes identify some challenges for further research.

In summary, the findings reinforce the importance of probabilistic approaches that capture uncertainties, spatial variability, and case-specific conditions. This is especially true for blended cements, where calibration against empirical evidence is essential before adopting generalized design rules. Transitioning from deterministic estimates to reliability-based approaches offers a path to more robust service-life predictions and more efficient durability design.

Acknowledgments

The research was co-funded by the European Union under the project INODIN, No. CZ.02.01.01/00/23_020/0008487 and by the Czech Science Foundation under Grant No. 23-06222S.

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